

ISic3417

I.Sicily inscription 3417

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

tufa limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Scicli

Provenance

Fondo Palmento della Grazia, nella contrada Barracche, tra Scicli e Sampieri

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa; Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Ibleo; Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6197; 6198

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491429

EDCS 51400892

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2008.0600

Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.
Vatican. At no.501

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*.
28-29: 3-29. At 29 no.102

Rizzone, V.G. 2008. Iscrizioni tardoantiche del territorio di Scicli. In Militello, P.
(eds.), *Scicli: archeologia e territorio*. Palermo. pp. 283-290. At 286-290 no.3
fig.25.3-4

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3417. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388538>